

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

ALIGNMENT AND REINFORCING POTENTIAL OF MULTIFILAMENT CNT FABRICS

A. Mikhalchan, C. Santos, and J. J. Vilatela

IMDEA Materials Institute, Madrid, Spain

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

<http://ontheworldmap.com/spain/spain-tourist-map.jpg>

<https://youtu.be/NXRszVtGovA>

<https://materials.imdea.org/>

Follow us

Looking up into the reactor

Continuous spinning of 1km

CNT fibres

CNT yarns (10-100 filament tow)

- ✓ Sensors
- ✓ Wearables
- ✓ Textiles

Direct synthesis of unidirectional multifilament CNT fabrics

- ✓ Electrodes, batteries, supercapacitors
- ✓ Thin interleaves (interlaminar reinforcement)
- ✓ Fabrics & preregs (large-scale composites)

Individual CNTs

CNT bundles

CNT fibres

CNT fabrics
(macro-scale)

A. Mikhalchan & J. J. Vilatela, Carbon 2019, 150:191-215

A. Mikhalchan & J. J. Vilatela, *Carbon* 2019, 150:191-215

Mechanical properties

Functional properties

Carbon fibre

CNT fibre

Fibre	Specific Strength (GPa/SG)	Specific Stiffness (GPa/SG)	Fracture Energy (J/g)	Specific surface area (m ² /g)
AS4 Carbon Fibre	2.4	127	22.4	0.2
CNT Fibre (MNG)	1 – 2	50 – 100	50 – 100	150 - 250

CNT Fibre

Traditional high-performance fibre
(Kevlar)

Fibrillar fracture
of PE fibres

Fibrillar fracture of CNT fibres

Vilatela, J. J., Elliott, J. A., & Windle, A. H. *Acs Nano* 2011, 5(3):1921-1927
A. Mikhailchun & J. J. Vilatela, *Carbon* 2019, 150:191-215

Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain

- Nanotubes are elastically stretched
- Nanotubes rotate towards the load direction (axis)

Fibrillar microstructure made of close packed CNT bundles

Schematic representation of a single CNT bundle and its contribution to the macroscopic deformation of the fibre

WAXS and SAXS patterns of CNT fibres
ODF for CNT yarns obtained at different draw ratios

WAXS (100 filaments)

SAXS (single filament)

Orientation effect

the stiffness of a CNT fibre is mainly dominated by CNT bundle alignment

SAXS patterns of CNT fabrics at different draw ratio

(a)

(b)

(c)

European Research Council
Established by the European Commission

Development of structural composite supercapacitor based on CNT fabrics/polymer electrolyte interleaves at IMDEA Materials Institute

Thank you!

Dr Anastasiia Mikhalchan

IMDEA Materials Institute
Multifunctional Nanocomposites Group

Eric Kandel, 2
Getafe, Madrid, Spain
28906
anastasiia.mikhalchan@imdea.org